
MASTER THESIS REPORT

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Modeling and simulation of a photovoltaic system and control of the nonlinear dynamics of the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) using artificial intelligence

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES.....	Erreur ! Signet non défini.
LIST OF TABLES.....	Erreur ! Signet non défini.
GENERAL INTRODUCTION	1
1 Chapter 01: Literature review.....	3
1.1 Introduction.....	4
1.2 State of the Art.....	4
1.3 Conclusion	14
2 Chapter 02 : Modeling of PV Systems	15
2.1 Introduction.....	16
2.2 Modeling of a permanent magnet synchronous machine	16
2.2.1 Description of the PMSM.....	17
2.2.2 Three phase PMSM model	18
2.2.3 Application of the Park Transformation:.....	21
2.2.4 Nonlinear dynamic state model of an PMSM	23
2.3 Three Phase Inverter	24
2.4 Modelling of a PV Cell	26
2.5 Pumping subsystem modelling.	29
2.6 MPPT Techniques.....	30
2.6.1 Perturb and Observe.....	30
2.6.2 Simulation and Results	31
2.7 Conclusion	41
3 Chapter 03: Implementation of MPPT controller by artificial intelligence.....	42
3.1 Introduction.....	43
3.2 Background of Neural Networks	43
3.3 The Proposed ANN Model	45
3.2.1 Collection of Data.....	46
3.2.2 Selection of ANN architecture	47
3.2.3 Training the network	51
3.2.4 Testing and validation	51

3.4	Simulation Results	51
3.5	Conclusion	59
	GENERAL CONCLUSION	60
	Bibliography.....	61
	Appendix A	70
	The Simulink model of a standalone a solar-powered (PV) water pump	70
	Appendix B.....	71
	Table B.1 System parameters for the Photovoltaic pumping	71
	Appendix C.....	73
	Data sheet of Sharp NU-S5E3E 185 PV module.....	73

LIST OF FIGURES

2-1 Representation of a synchronous machine with permanent magnets.....	17
2-2 Symbolic representation of the MSAP	18
2-3 Park Principle.....	22
2-4 Three-phase full-bridge inverter topology	25
2-5 PV systems types	27
2-6 PV cell equivalent model	28
2-7 The standard P&O algorithm's flowchart	31
2-8 Sun powered irradiance and temperature for a normal day of August	32
2-9 test system of PV modules.....	32
2-10 A 3D surface of the PV panel's properties at constant 1000 Wm ² solar irradiance with different temperatures	34
2-11 A 3D surface of the characteristic of PV panel at constant temperature 25 °C with different solar irradiance.....	35
2-12 P&O controller for PV motor pumping system.	35
2-13 Solar irradiance	36
2-14 PV array output for the conventional P&O method under a various solar irradiation levels: (a) voltage, (b) current, and (c) power.....	37
2-15 Phase voltage and current	38
2-16 q-axis and d-axis voltage and current	39
2-17 Output torque	40
2-18 Reference and PMSM speeds	40
3-1 A basic artificial neuron.....	44
3-2 Proposed ANN controller for PV motor pumping system.	45
3-3 ANN_Current_Reference q-axis PMSM	48
3-4 ANN_Current_Reference d-axis PMSM	49
3-5 ANN_Voltage_Reference dq-axis and d-axis PMSM	50
3-6 The training regression results for ANN-MPPT controle.....	52
3-7 Performance of PMSM for various reference speeds: case 1	54
3-8 Performance of PMSM for various reference speeds: case 2	55
3-9 Performance of PMSM for various reference speeds: case 3	56
3-10 Performance of PMSM for various reference speeds: case 4	57
3-11 torque	58

3-12 Performances of the PV system compared between MPPT with P&O and the suggested ANN approach	59
A.1 A standalone PV water pumping system's Simulink model, based on MATLAB simulation	70

LIST OF TABLES

1.1 Comparison of different MPPT algorithms.....	13
3.1 Samples data's from the conventional method used in the Chapter2 test	47
B.1 System parameters for the PV pumping	71

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

In rural areas, one of the most cost-effective ways to power water pumps is through photovoltaic (PV) energy systems. The importance of photovoltaic energy systems is due to its low cost, dependability, and maintainability. Photovoltaic systems are difficult because of the nonlinear and time-varying characteristics of solar modules and switching converters. A solar array, a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) controller, a DC/AC inverter, and associated controllers make up the majority of photovoltaic power generation systems. As a result, the entire model is a nonlinear multivariate system, and the weather has an impact on how well it performs. PV generators may be utilized alone, in conjunction with a pumping system, or in addition to a battery. From the standpoint of stability, the latter is the best choice because it provides consistent performance. The collected energy will also be usable at night at the same time. Although scholars have been looking for a solution, energy storage is an expensive option. However, it is preferable to connect directly to the pump system because it might help you save some money. Nevertheless, the power generated is susceptible to variations and losses since photovoltaic energy is brittle. In photovoltaics, it is important to operate the system in an energy efficient manner and maximize power consumption by maintaining the peak power point of the system, paying little attention to changes in load and environmental factors.

A MPPT system has been built to enable this, enabling the delivery of the solar array's maximum power while tracking fluctuations in maximum power brought on by changes in the meteorological conditions. Temperature (T) and solar irradiation (G) are the two key factors that determine how much electrical power a photovoltaic system can generate. Minimizing losses and enhancing overall system performance are essential for any photovoltaic power generating system, including PV water pumping systems. Although there are a number of MPPT strategies, perturb and observe (P&O) is the most used MPPT method nowadays. When atmospheric conditions are unpredictable, a P&O approach makes it challenging to attain both the best steady state operating conditions and an efficient power extraction. When using solar generation, it's important to maintain the system's peak power point while paying little attention to changes in load and environmental conditions in order to maximize power extraction.

Artificial intelligence (AI) approaches, particularly those from machine learning (ML), are becoming more and more beneficial as add-ons to current procedures or as components of integrated

systems. They are becoming more widespread these days and have been applied to solve challenging real-world issues across several sectors. Fault tolerant examples can be utilized for learning in that they can deal with noise and incomplete data, manage nonlinear issues, and make predictions and generalizations to high speed electrical equipment.

The manuscript is structured as follows: The first chapter gives an outline of the bibliographic analysis, which compares and categorizes current studies on various MPPT approaches according to their most salient characteristics. The modeling, structure, and controller of the photovoltaic system are covered in the second chapter. A Matlab Simulink model for a stand-alone PV water pump system is made using the conventional P&O approach. The findings of the simulation are then displayed and discussed. In the third chapter, we provide an MPPT approach for PV water pumping systems that is based on artificial neural networks. This method would guarantee both system stability and electricity extraction. Following that, the design of the suggested ANN controller and its operating principles, including its learning and testing procedures, are given. The key characteristics of the recommended approach are then contrasted with those of P&O.

1

Chapter 01: Literature review

TABLE OF CONTENT

1.1	Introduction.....	4
1.2	State of the Art	4
1.3	Conclusion	14

1.1 Introduction

Solar energy has gained a lot of interest in recent decades as a result of its environmental friendliness, availability, and low maintenance requirements due to the rising development in electrical energy use and the depletion of fossil fuels. In remote areas, it is used for illumination, water pumping, and other purposes. Still, carrying the peak power generated by the PV at any time of day is important since the nonlinear PV features make it challenging to detect the peak power point (MPP). MPPT technology is thus needed to boost power product. Several methods have been developed to find MPP throughout the past few decades. The number of sensors employed, their complexity, cost, practical range, speed of convergence, how well they follow changes in temperature and/or irradiance, the hardware required for implementation, and other factors all vary between these systems. In this chapter, some of the most well-known MPPT methods are introduced.

1.2 State of the Art

The voltage and current combination at which solar photovoltaic cells produce the most power is known as the maximum power point (MPP). When it reaches the PV cells, the solar radiation's intensity and temperature determine its electric characteristics. Adequate control is required to operate in accordance with the MPP and maintain the best solar power output possible. To do this, maximum power point tracking is employed. The MPP's PV panels are intended to be monitored and controlled by the MPPT control system regardless of adjustments or environmental changes. For locating and monitoring the MPP functioning, there are many tried-and-true MPPT procedures.

Although conventional methods have been used by researchers in solar energy applications, the Perturb & Observe (P&O) method is the most popular. This process typically oscillates around the ideal value and is highly reliant on the initial circumstances [1]. The primary weakness of this algorithm is its problematic behavior following a sudden change in solar irradiation; poor follow-up with varied irradiance and excessive oscillations around MPP. In [38], a constant voltage controller (CVC) based alternative to the conventional MPPT method is proposed. However, it performs poorly in erratic weather, particularly when the PV panel's temperature varies. Another conventional MPPT controller for a PV system was introduced in [34], the incremental conductance algorithm (INC) model, which tracks the MPP point under varying weather conditions. The PV module's current and

voltage serve as the suggested INC technique's inputs, and its output is the ideal duty cycle for a power generation system. The literature contains numerous alternative modified variations of this technique, such as in [35], where the authors proposed a modified INC algorithm in order to locate the global peak (GP) under both uniform irradiance conditions (UIC). The outcomes showed that the suggested strategy is more straightforward and effective than alternate options. Comparing the proposed approach to the conventional INC, tracking efficiency is also increased overall. These techniques possess elegant benefits including being easy to program and use. They are unable to guarantee a goal GMPP, however, due to changing environmental conditions [55]. They lose influence because they can't tell the global power apart from all other points.

Researchers have looked into another type of MPPT methodology that is based on the optimization approach to overcome the drawbacks of the conventional methodologies. [6-7] are some of these researchers. Compared to simulated annealing (SA), tabu search (TS), and harmony search (HS) particle swarm optimization (PSO) is said to give more promising outcomes. Of the four well-known metaheuristic algorithms employed in [8], PSO is also the most reliable. The PSO is one of the powerful algorithms that takes inspiration from studies on the flocking behavior of birds in the wild because it has the ability to target random functions. However, the traditional application of this method has a number of flaws, including constant particle velocity, a heavy reliance on random coefficients, and delayed convergence, which increases tracking time. Numerous studies have attempted to solve these issues by improving upon the effectiveness of traditional PSO. The main benefit of the MPSO, according to the authors of [9], is the decrease in steady state oscillation after the MPP. Improved PSO in [10] outperforms P&O and INC in terms of tracking speed and convergence. However, there are still some issues with the upgraded version. In one work, the metaheuristic characteristics of evolutionary algorithms were minimized using a deterministic PSO approach and removed random coefficients [53].

Different evolution-based methods, such as the genetic algorithm (GA), differential evolution (DE), grey wolf (GWO), and the firework algorithm (FWA) (LMPP), are used to determine the multiple local maximal output of a GMPP partially shaded photovoltaic system [51–52]. Using the grey wolf optimization method, MPPT was used in [40] to construct solar arrays. With regard to P&O and advanced PSO techniques, GWO, a new optimization strategy, overcomes the drawbacks of tracking inefficiencies, steady state oscillations, and transients. A issue arises while trying to track a PV array's global peak (GP) in partial shade conditions (PSC) using GWO-based MPPT technology.

To confirm the efficacy of the suggested system, an experimental setup is also created. The suggested MPPT method beats the P&O and PSO because it is more dependable and has a faster rate of convergence, as shown by the simulation and experimental findings. In [39], a fresh MPPT technique based on the modified butterfly optimization (MBOA) algorithm is proposed. The suggested approach quickly converges and can distinguish between a variety of local shadow patterns, uniform shadows, sun intensity, and load shifting scenarios. Using a single dynamic variable as the tuning parameter streamlines the process. The main advantages of this MPPT controller are the direct control of duty cycle, avoidance of PID/PI tuning, removal of the requirement to implement PV parameters in the controller, simplicity of the control structure, minimization of calculation, and lack of requirement for high memory microcontrollers. Metaheuristic approaches are more challenging to apply than conventional MPPT procedures, though.

Artificial intelligence (AI) methods have been used more and more in solar systems in recent years. This is due to the fact that it may address important problems with both traditional and optimized MPPT procedures. Additionally, these methods don't need intricate mathematics or exact specifications for system management. Due to its high response and low oscillation, the fuzzy logic controller (FLC), when compared to traditional MPPT approaches, is one of the most efficient intelligent controllers for a PV system.

The FLC method was employed by the authors of [2] to implement the MPP. They show that FLC outperforms the P&O algorithm. Fast power tracking, reduced oscillation, and steady operation are also displayed. In [3], it is demonstrated that the tracking mechanism of the MPP in solar systems uses fuzzy type logic controllers, which is another use of fuzzy control. They are dependable and relatively easy to create, among their many other benefits. Other studies, like [4], have reported getting similar outcomes. A study of an intelligent MPPT for a standalone PV system is presented in [5].

The obtained simulation results showed that the proposed method performed better than the well-known MPPT method P&O. In reaction to shifting weather conditions, the fuzzy logic controller boosts output power, reduces fluctuation, and offers short response times. The drift problem phenomena linked to a change in the operation's temperature and radiation level, however, is the main problem [14]. This is because it depends heavily on having a thorough understanding of PV systems, which results in inaccurate membership functions. Numerous modulations have been suggested to address this problem, such as an enhanced membership function of the conventional FLC MPPT, as illustrated in [20]. However, the execution has grown unnecessarily complicated.

Numerous research initiatives have focused on the application of machine learning (ML) methods to solar system control. The efficiency of solar systems has increased as a result of these efforts, which have improved the maximum power point tracking procedure. Machine learning (ML), which begins with unprocessed input, feature extraction, preprocessing and normalization, training and scoring, and model deployment, enables a machine to predict outcomes without being explicitly programmed. The feasibility of using ML-based MPPT to make the most of solar systems' maximum power when subject to PSC was examined in the work [61]. Some progress in the sectors of solar systems and ML-based systems has been made by presenting three tests carried out in diverse climates and providing nine ML-based MPPT approaches. Bag Trees (BT), Naive Bayes Classifiers (NBC), Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Weighted K-Nearest Neighbors (WK-NN), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), and Support Vector Machines (SVM) make up the majority of these techniques. The experimental findings showed that SVM and RNN approaches outperform all other methods in terms of accuracy and computation time. BT and WK-NN are the least accurate of all the approaches. Even if the NBC has a lengthy computation time, building one is expensive and challenging.

Artificial neural networks (ANN) are yet another effective intelligent technique for a nonlinear system like a PV. The primary benefits of using ANN with PV MPPT systems are that it offers a comprehensive solution for a variety of problems and doesn't necessitate a deep understanding of internal system characteristics[36]. The authors of [11] take two steps in the construction of an ANN-based MPPT controller: offline tuning of neural network parameters, and live application of the optimal ANN MPPT controller for MPPT. The ANN controller outperforms the P&O technique in terms of convergence and oscillations, according to modeling and experimental results.

The comparison between the neural network method for MPP tracking and the P&O algorithm for MPPT is shown in [12]. Compared to MPPT based on the conventional P&O method, neural network algorithms can anticipate results more accurately.

The neural network's capacity to predict the maximum power point of the PV array was tested using a range of irradiance levels and temperatures. A comparison of MPPT utilizing the P&O approach and without the MPPT tracker is also shown in [13]. The findings show that the neural network-based MPPT tracking requires less time and yields more accurate results when compared to MPPT based on the P&O method. An MPPT technique has been built using the radial basis function network (RBFN) and neural network (ANN) algorithms.

Temperature and voltage data are used as input in the proposed ANN-based MPPT technique, which has been examined in [37]. In the suggested method, the reference voltage is created by the output of the ANN structure and is managed by a proportional integral (PI) controller. By contrasting its response time, power fluctuation, and efficiency in various weather circumstances with that of conventional P&O and IC approaches, its performance is discussed. The results highlight the excellent performance of the suggested technique, which provides the quickest response time and highest efficiency for both steady state and irradiance variations.

Similarity, the authors of [45] offers a technique for monitoring the maximum power point that can be utilized to use inverters to distribute electrical energy from PV modules to three-phase independent loads. Based on asymmetrical ANN functions, the method is used. The suggested ANN-MPPT technique offers a single controller to maximize the output of three PV panels coupled to three phase independent inverters rather than employing three MPPT algorithms and three duty cycle controllers. Low common mode voltage (CMV), superior power quality, and capacitor voltage balancing with less ripple are the outcomes. The authors of [21] provide a study on photovoltaic energy conversion chains' optimum performance tracking. Two methods for tracking maximum power were compared; the first way uses P&O, whereas the second method uses (ANN). They suggest an MPPT-based ANN to improve power electronic converter (PEC) performance in all air conditions and compare the outcomes to conventional P&O techniques. The boost converter's output, the duty cycle, is used to measure the MPP of the solar array.

The input ANN uses the electrical parameter that was received from the PV array under various meteorological conditions. The simulation results show that the ANN based MPPT has better dynamic and fast reaction performance and less steady state oscillations under rapidly fluctuating solar irradiation. Conversely, when irradiance fluctuates quickly, P&O technology is unable to track MPP. The authors adopted a slightly different strategy from that of [23] and created a reliable and useful tool for determining the maximum power point of photovoltaics. This tool was created utilizing trustworthy experimental datasets. The link between current and maximum power voltage (V_{mp}) (I_{mp}) on one side, comparison and study on insolation data, electrical parameters, thermal parameters, and meteorological parameters were labor-intensive and time-consuming. To reduce MPP estimation error, several input circumstances are compared. Four scenarios based on various PV parameter combinations and numerous ANN-based MPP IDs are provided, assessed using the most common regression metric (MSE) mean squared error, and then compared in order to improve the accuracy of

the MPP identification. In terms of performance and dynamic reactivity, the suggested concepts perform better than traditional methods. Getting a reliable training dataset is a big challenge when designing an optimal ANNMPPT method.

Deep learning (DL) algorithms, a branch of machine learning, are built on the ANN (ML). The feature extraction stage is purposely omitted in DL since DL algorithms are capable of learning from and autonomously extracting features from raw input data [64]. Deep learning (DL), a new advancement in ANN, is a technique for training deep neural networks (DNN). Deep belief networks (DBNN), long short term memory, and deep convolutional neural networks (DCNN) are the main DL techniques employed in photovoltaic applications (LSTM). The authors of [59] proposed a technique based on maximum power point tracking. The creation of a sophisticated deep learning controller that reduces harmonic distortion overall and enhances power quality

In order to improve the maximum power point provided by solar arrays and overcome the shortcomings of traditional MPPT algorithms under changing irradiation circumstances, a hybrid MPPT was developed [44]. In order to train an artificial neural network (ANN) and create concatenated weights and biases to determine the ideal value of the duty cycle converter, which corresponds to the maximum power point for photovoltaic arrays, the proposed method, known as the ACO-ANN MPPT controller and based on the ant colony optimization algorithm, can be used (MPP). Because of its flexible automation to track MPP is effective under changes in irradiance and has less variation in MPP compared to traditional INC methods, the hybrid ANN based ACO algorithm has been successfully used to find continuous variables for problems with optimization in a large number of power systems. The results demonstrated that the suggested GA-optimized ANN-based MPPT technique in [16] satisfied the requirement for the ideal power supply and minimized fluctuations around the operating point. To extract MPP from the available solar energy, a metaheuristic optimized multilayer artificial neural network (MLP) feedforward controller is provided.

In the paper [42], it is discussed how to use a hybrid strategy of shuffling frog hop and pattern search to optimize ANN-based MPPT in grid-connected solar systems. This approach was developed to meet a number of network requirements, such as improved network quality and distortion-free communications (HSFL-PS). After ANN training and choosing neuron weights, the P&O technique is utilized to track the recurrent process and starts an exact tracking scheme. Partial shadowing (PS) is less harmful thanks to bypass diodes, and leads to a diversity of peak characteristics at the solar

system's output.

Conventional MPPT algorithms may make mistakes and find local maximum power points instead of global maximum power points (LMPP). Various AI-based strategies have been used to change how well conventional controllers function. These methods, however, either fall short of solving the PS problem completely or give rise to exceedingly complex and unreliable methods that require additional research before being applied to high-speed applications. In this study, adaptive radial motion optimization (ARMO), a new expedient, reliable, and reasonably priced method to simplify the PV systems' PS problem to MPP detection, was devised, developed, and validated [41].

Faster tracking and notably lower production fluctuation when tracking are two of ARMO's main advantages. Extensive experimental validation is done when utilized with special PV systems and DC/DC converters to fairly compare the suggested strategy to conventional and more modern solutions under similar circumstances. A new MPPT approach is proposed in [18] for a PV system with constant irradiation. It was created using System Identification SI and is known as SI based polynomial ARV. Using a basic polynomial-based model, the reference voltage is determined.

The effectiveness of the suggested strategy is examined. The outcomes were compared to and evaluated using P&O, incremental conductance, constant voltage reference CVR, and ANN-based ARV. The simulation results show that the proposed method is simple in structure, reliable in applicability, and functionally efficient. An effective three-dimensional tuning method and a time-based maximum power point tracking (TB-MPPT) circuit are reported in [19]. To reduce significant losses from charge redistribution, the conversion ratio is selected based on the strength of the input voltage. The proposed algorithm may locate the highest power point with the least amount of tuning, switching frequency, and capacity control, aiming to decrease power loss and improve power conversion efficiency.

An adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) has been used to control the maximum power point of a PV solar system, as reported in [15-71]. A hybrid MPPT algorithm that performs better while the environment is changing was developed using several methods. It was found that under various irradiation settings, the ANFIS controller efficiently extracted the greatest power from the panel while providing a very quick stable response. Performance of the proposed ANFIS-based MPPT scheme is compared to that of the conventional MPPT system based on P&O algorithms.

The proposed approach is found to provide a faster response with appreciably less oscillations than the traditional MPPT technique. Numerous studies [46–47] on IA methods like FLC and ANN have

been conducted. The effectiveness and dependability of the MPP tracking controllers under usual conditions are increased in some of this research using FLC. For instance, in [48], the authors increased the efficiency and tracking speed of the HC approach by using FLC. In the first stage of this inquiry, FLC was used to scan and store MPP regions, and in the second stage, HC was used to track the actual MPP. In a different study, it was hypothesized that daytime cell temperature and irradiance may be used to monitor the solar systems' worldwide maximum power point. As a result, the trained ANN is used to operate the FLC-based MPPT controller as a good supervisor [49].

These studies used a variety of methodologies to estimate the GMPP in a variety of common and uncommon scenarios, with satisfactory results. However, due to the computationally expensive nature of the ‘fuzzification’, ‘rule basis’, ‘defuzzification’, and training processes, these strategies have some drawbacks [50]. The paper [14] provides an innovative MPPT algorithm that combines the effective ANN-CGSVM methodology with the coarse Gaussian support vector machine (CGSVM). The results showed that the hybrid ANN-P&O MPPT technique effectively reduced the issue of oscillating power near MPP that is usual with conventional P&O MPPT technique. Both the ANN-CGSVM and the ANN-PO techniques also showed a high convergence speed. The suggested CGSVM technique can be used to obtain reasonable maximum performance and has a quick tracking speed.

The most economical choice, especially in rural regions, is considered to be photovoltaic independent water pumping systems. One of the several MPPT techniques published in the literature, the study in [24–25] used an adaptive neuro-fuzzy controller to model and vector regulates PV pump systems. Additionally, a smooth vector control system linked to neural networks is developed and evaluated for effectiveness. The main goal of this study was to enhance optimization methods to increase the overall efficacy of the pumping system.

To boost its energy efficiency under all circumstances, they installed a maximum power point adapter between the inverter and the photovoltaic generator. This study found that sliding neuron control performed better than other approaches in terms of reducing deviations from the reference and enhancing flutter issues. Researchers have studied solar water pumping systems [22]. The system consists of three main parts: a PVG, a boost converter from DC to DC, and a DC motor coupled to a centrifugal water pump.

A fuzzy controller manages the DC-DC boost converter, and an artificial neural network forecasts the ideal PV voltage under various environmental factors (temperature and solar radiation). We propose a maximum power tracker based on ANN and FL technology and compare it to MPPT based

on P&O technology. The P&O technology is then put up against the suggested tactic in comparison. The simulation's findings prove that the MPPT based on ANN and fuzzy logic is superior. It has been established that the algorithm works better since it is more precise, responsive to shifting weather conditions, and has a rapid response time. One of the options for the initial stage of using the photovoltaic array to power the motor pump was whether or not to employ a backup battery of any capacity [25]. For instance, it was shown in [26-27-28] that operating a motor with equivalent power from a PV array causes considerable changes in mechanical performance parameters that are predicated on the motor's rotational speed. Regardless of whether the magnetic fields are generated in parallel, series, or independently, the motor shaft still produces torque in all types of DC motors.

Further research reveals that the MC parameters are influenced by the nominal power of the PV array, the lighting and its fluctuations throughout the day, as well as the connection circuit of the PV modules. When a photovoltaic system of comparable power powers the DC motor, as was done in study [29-30], these typical characteristics significantly change. In particular, the starting torque ratio is reduced. Through the use of optimization techniques, it was shown in [3],[32-33] that flux weakening is the most effective strategy to regulate the speed of a DC motor. Additionally, they are easy to use with single, parallel, or series excited motors.

According to implementation difficulties, cost, the number of sensor parameters, oscillation, tracking speed, and tracking efficacy, Table 1.1 lists the advantages and disadvantages of each MPPT algorithm,

Algorithms	Reference	Implementation complexity	Cost	Sensed Parameters	Oscillation	Tracking Speed	Tracking Efficiency
P&O	[1-16-17-52]	Simple	Inexpensive	I,V	High	Fast	Low
INC	[34-35]	Simple	Inexpensive	I,V	High	Fast	Medium
HC	[60]	Simple	Inexpensive	I,V	High	Slow	Low
CVC	[38]	Simple	Inexpensive	I,V	High	Slow	Low
ARV	[18]	Complex	Inexpensive	I,V	High	Slow	Medium
RCC	[56]	Simple	Inexpensive	I,V	High	Fast	Low

CV	[62]	Simple	Inexpensive	V	High	Slow	Low
CC	[60-62]	Simple	Inexpensive	I	High	Slow	Low
PSO	[10-20-9]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Fast	Medium
TS	[7-8]	Simple	Inexpensive	Varies	High	Slow	Medium
SA	[6-7]	Simple	Inexpensive	Varies	High	Slow	Medium
HS	[6-8]	Simple	Inexpensive	I,V	Medium	Slow	Low
GA	[57]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Fast	Low
DE	[8]	Complex	Inexpensive	I,V	Medium	Slow	Medium
GWO	[40-54]	Complex	Expensive	I,V	Medium	Medium	Medium
MBOA	[39]	Complex	Expensive	I,V	Medium	Medium	Low
ANN	[11-12-45]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Low	Fast	High
DNN	[59-61-64]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Low	Fast	High
k-NN	[61-63]	Complex	Expensive	I,V	Medium	Slow	Medium
NB	[63]	Simple	Expensive	I,V,P	Medium	Medium	Medium
FLC	[2-3-4]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Fast	Medium
SVM	[14]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Fast	Medium
SI-ARV	[41]	Complex	Expensive	I,V,P	High	Fast	Medium
ANN-PO	[21-42]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Fast	High
FLC-GA	[48]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Fast	Medium
ANN-PSO	[31]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Low	Fast	Medium
ANN-ACO	[44]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Slow	Medium
ACO-GA	[43]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Slow	Medium
ANN-SVM	[14]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Fast	High
ANN-FLC	[46-47-50]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Low	Fast	High
PSO-FLC	[56-58]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Medium	High
FLC-P&O	[16]	Complex	Expensive	Varies	Medium	Fast	Medium

Table 1.1 Comparison of several MPPT algorithms

The various MPPT techniques covered above are appropriate for a variety of uses. MPP trackers'

cost and complexity are not as important as their efficiency and durability, much like pricey space satellites and orbiting stations. The tracker should not require routine tuning and should be able to follow the real MPP continuously in the shortest amount of time. Machine learning and deep learning, more specifically neural networks and deep neural networks, are appropriate in this situation. Specifically, solar cars must soon converge at MPP. Artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques, particularly FLC and ANN, are sensible alternatives in this situation. The majority of the load on a solar car is made up of batteries, thus optimizing the load current or voltage is equally important. PV generator deployment in residential locations needs to be quick and continuous MPP tracking in order to shorten the payback period. Due to the possibility of partial shadows (from trees and other structures), MPPT must be able to steer clear of a few local maxima. Metaheuristics are useful in this case. All day long, solar street lighting systems only require rechargeable batteries. Stringent requirements may not be required; rather, a simple and cost-effective implementation may be more important, enabling the use of P&O, INC, and RCC traditional approaches. Most importantly, a photovoltaic water pumping system would require an MPP in order to extract electricity, track more precisely, track faster, and oscillate less. Machine learning is an excellent substitute in that case. Due to the possibility of batteries being employed in a water pumping system, hybrid approaches like MPPT can also be applied. Since they can maximize electricity, these methods demonstrate that a PV system may be used as the primary power source in addition to being a more cost-effective and environmentally friendly energy source.

1.3 Conclusion

A broad review of the various MPPT methods based on those qualities has been given in this chapter. The advantages and disadvantages of each MPPT method have also been defined and addressed. The conventional, metaheuristic, artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, and hybrid techniques have been contrasted in terms of their key features. According to the evaluation's findings, MPPT controllers that use AI, ML, and DL approaches are more complex, expensive, and challenging to deploy. In contrast to the traditional MPPT methods, they have a greater tracking efficiency, a faster tracking speed, and less oscillation.

2

Chapter 02 : Modeling of PV Systems

TABLE OF CONTENT

2.1	Introduction	16
2.2	Modeling of a permanent magnet synchronous machine	16
2.2.1	Description of the PMSM.....	17
2.2.2	Three phase PMSM model	18
2.2.3	Application of the Park Transformation:	21
2.2.4	Nonlinear dynamic state model of an PMSM	23
2.3	Three Phase Inverter	24
2.4	Modelling of a PV Cell.....	26
2.5	Pumping subsystem modelling.....	29
2.6	MPPT Techniques	30
2.6.1	Perturb and Observe	30
2.6.2	Simulation and Results.....	31
2.7	Conclusion.....	41

2.1 Introduction

In order to maintain ecosystems, ensure food production, provide energy, and advance social, economic, and societal development, water resources are crucial. However, the lack of drinking water and the impact of water scarcity on people in many dry nations make the need for it urgent. A self-contained pumping system is essential in addressing this need when there is no main system accessible. However, the photovoltaic energy generated by such devices must be properly managed and optimized. A variety of control methods that have been published in the literature have been used to track the maximum power point of a solar array. Although they are capable of doing the same task with great efficiency and rapid speed in a variety of environmental conditions, these control systems have different conceptual frameworks (sunlight and temperature). Synchronous permanent magnet machines (PMSM)-based PV pumping systems are widely utilized because they are more dependable, inexpensive, and need little ongoing maintenance.

The chapter is organized as follows: The structures and modeling of a DC-AC converter, a PV cell, and a centrifugal pump are presented in Sections 2.3, 2.4, and 2.5, respectively. Section 2.2 describes and models a synchronous permanent magnet machine. In part 2.6, a matlab simulink model for a standalone PV water pump system is built using a conventional P&O MPPT controller. Following that, the simulation results are presented and debated. A summary and chapter conclusion are given in Section 2.7.

2.2 Permanent magnet synchronous machine modeling

Any physical system investigation requires modeling. As a result, we can model how this system responds to various demands and better understand the mechanisms driving its operation. Modern and more effective control rules enable better transient speed control while guaranteeing precise speed control over a wide working range. All of these enhancements call for thorough understanding of the machine and its converter, particularly under transient conditions. In our situation, design laws tailored to PMSM will be derived [69].

2.2.1 Description of the PMSM

Electric motors can be broadly categorized into three groups: synchronous motors, induction

motors (IM), and DC motors. The synchronous permanent magnet motor is one of these motor types, and it has a stationary component called the stator and a moving component called the rotor, like other electric machines do. Electrical energy is transformed into mechanical energy by electric motors, which are electromechanical devices. As shown in figure 2.1, the PMSM has three phases of winding on the stator that are symbolized by the three axes (a, b, and c) phase displaced by 120 degrees from one another and permanent magnets in the rotor to assure its excitation.

Figure 2-1 Illustration of a permanent magnet synchronous machine

The permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) has undergone substantial development for usage in industrial and domestic applications due to its high power density, high power factor; high efficiency, superior control performance, and low torque ripple characteristics. However, due to a PMSM's nonlinearity and the close coupling of its variables, its dynamic behavior is complex [67-68],[70],[19]

2.2.2 Three phase PMSM model

Figure 2-2 Symbolic representation of the MSAP

A set of six differential equations with variable coefficients makes up a PMSM mathematical model. The system of equations is quite challenging to study. Even with computer tools, solving such a system is tough. Therefore, a more basic model needs to be created. Under some simple assumptions, the park can be changed to solve the problem. The control model's complexity is significantly reduced because it provides a two-phase representation of an engine that is comparable to a three-phase engine.

❖ **Simplifying assumptions**

The following simplifying assumptions are made in the MSAP model:

- Saturation is ignored, therefore individual and mutual inductances are independent of the currents flowing through the different windings.
- The notching effect is disregarded, the fmm are sinusoidal in the machine's air space and the magnetic axis of the windings is symmetrical.
- Eddy currents and hysteresis in magnetic components are not taken into account.

The following equations can be used to describe the dynamic model of a permanent magnet synchronous motor:

❖ **Electrical equation**

The synchronous machine equations the stator reference frame are as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} R_s & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R_s \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{pmatrix} + \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} \phi_a \\ \phi_b \\ \phi_c \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.1)$$

In reduced form, it is written as:

$$[v_s] = [R_s][i_s] + \frac{d}{dt}[\phi_s] \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{With: } [v_s] = [v_a \ v_b \ v_c]^T ; [i_s] = [i_a \ i_b \ i_c]^T ; [\phi_s] = [\phi_a \ \phi_b \ \phi_c]^T ; [R_s] = \begin{pmatrix} R_s & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R_s \end{pmatrix}$$

Where:

v_a, v_b and v_c are the voltages across each individual stator winding for each phase

R_s is each stator winding's corresponding resistance

$i_a, i_b,$ and i_c are the stator windings currents

ϕ_a, ϕ_b and ϕ_c are the rates of magnetic flux variation with in each stator winding.

The vector form of the total flows $[\phi_s]$ is written in the following form:

$$[\phi_s] = [L_s][i_s] + [\phi_{sf}] \quad (2.3)$$

$$[L_s] = [L_{s0}] + [L_{s2}] \quad (2.4)$$

$[L_s]$ Being the matrix of stator inductances,

With:

$$[L_{s0}] = \begin{pmatrix} L_{s0} & M_{s0} & M_{s0} \\ M_{s0} & L_{s0} & M_{s0} \\ M_{s0} & M_{s0} & L_{s0} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

According to Figure 2.2, the stator matrix inductance which depends on rotor position θ_r is given by:

$$[L_{S2}] = \phi_{s2} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(2\theta) & \cos(2\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(2\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \cos(2\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(2\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(2\theta) \\ \cos(2\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(2\theta) & \cos(2\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

And

$$[\phi_{sf}] = \phi_f \begin{pmatrix} \cos(2\theta) \\ \cos(2\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \cos(2\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.7)$$

$[\phi_{sf}] = [\phi_{af} \phi_{bf} \phi_{cf}]^T$, being the permanent magnet flow on the stator phases. Where, $\theta = p\theta_r$ is the electrical angle and θ_r is the rotor's mechanical position with respect to the stator.

To study the machine operation in all states, the following electrical system equations are used:

$$[v_s] = [R_s][i_s] + \frac{d\{[L_s][i_s]\}}{dt} + \frac{d[\phi_{sf}]}{dt} \quad (2.8)$$

This yield

$$[v_s] = [R_s][i_s] + \left([L_s] \frac{d[i_s]}{dt} \right) + \omega_r \frac{d[L_s]}{d\theta} [i_s] + \omega_r \frac{d[\phi_{sf}]}{d\theta} \quad (2.9)$$

❖ Mechanical equations:

The inductance matrix and the permanent magnet flux linkage are both impacted by the rotor position. In order to fully describe the motor using Newton's law, the mechanical equation of the rotor must be included in the motor model. The mechanical equation is presented as follows:

$$J \frac{d\Omega_r}{dx} + f_r \Omega_r = T_{em} - T_L \quad (2.10)$$

$$\omega_r = p\Omega_r \quad (2.11)$$

- J : moment of inertia

- T_{em} : the electromagnetic torque delivered by the motor
- T_L : the strong torque put on the motor shaft
- Ω_r : the motor angular speed
- f_r : viscous damping coefficient
- p : number of poles

❖ Electromagnetic torque of the PMSM

According to the derivative of mechanical energy in relation to the electrical position of the rotor, the electromagnetic torque produced by a machine can be calculated as follows:

$$T_{em} = \frac{1}{2} p [i_s]^T \left[\frac{d[L_s]}{d\theta} \right] [i_s] \quad (2.12)$$

By showing the stator and rotor quantities in the equation (2.12), and after simplification, we arrive at the following electromagnetic torque formula:

$$T_{em} = \frac{1}{2} p \left[\frac{1}{2} [i_s]^T \frac{d[L_s]}{d\theta} [i_s] + [i_s]^T \frac{d[\phi_{sf}]}{d\theta} \right] \quad (2.13)$$

Given the quantity of differential equations with variable coefficients, it is clear from previous equations that studying this system is highly challenging. We will apply mathematical transformations (Park and Clark) to this issue in order to find a solution. These transformations allow us to employ differential equations with constant coefficients to describe the behavior of the engine.

2.2.3 Application of the Park's Transformation:

Park's transformation is frequently referred to as a two-axis transformation. Physically, applying this transformation to the MSAP refers to splitting the three coils (stators) into two equivalent coils, taking into account the same factors or aspects in terms of flow, torque, or at the very least, producing an image that is exactly proportional to them. A single transformation matrix is established for currents, voltages, and flows. The transformation changes the abc variables into a new set of variables known as the dqo variables. It is orthogonal and nevertheless maintains the invariance of power. Additionally, it posits the null value for all homopolar quantities.

Applying the abc to dqo transformation [65-66],[69], we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 [V_{dqo}] &= [T][v_{abs}] \\
 [I_{dqo}] &= [T][i_{abs}] \\
 [\phi_{dqo}] &= [T][\phi_{abs}]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.14}$$

Where

$$[T] = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \cos(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ -\sin(\theta) & -\sin(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & -\sin(\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}
 \tag{2.15}$$

And

$$[T^{-1}] = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) & 1 \\ \cos(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & -\sin(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & 1 \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) & -\sin(\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) & 1 \end{pmatrix}
 \tag{2.16}$$

With $[T],[T^{-1}]$ are the matrices of direct and inverse passage.

Figure 2-3 Park Principle

The fictitious positions of the two coils d and q after the transformation are shown in Figure 2.3. Applying the Park $[T(\varphi)]$ transformation to the stator equation (2.2) can be rewritten as follows:

$$[T(\varphi)]^{-1}[V_{dqo}] = [R_s][T(\varphi)]^{-1}[i_{dqo}] + \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right) ([T(\varphi)]^{-1}[\phi_{dqo}]) \quad (2.17)$$

By multiplying both sides of (2.17) by $[T]$, we obtain:

$$[V_{dqo}] = [R_s][i_{dqo}] + \frac{d[\phi_{dqo}]}{dt} + [T(\varphi)] \left(\frac{d[T(\varphi)]^{-1}}{dt} \right) [\phi_{dqo}] \quad (2.18)$$

Hence, the normalized voltages could be presented as:

$$\begin{cases} V_d = R_s i_d + \frac{d\phi_d}{dt} - \frac{d\varphi}{dt} \phi_q \\ V_q = R_s i_q + \frac{d\phi_q}{dt} - \frac{d\varphi}{dt} \phi_d \\ V_0 = R_s i_0 + \frac{d\phi_0}{dt} \end{cases} \quad (2.19)$$

The third equation, V_0 , for a three-phase balanced system of tension is always zero. The flux linkages in dq variables as follows: Consider Equation (2.3)

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_d &= L_d I_d + \phi_f \\ \phi_q &= L_q I_q \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

If the Park frame is linked to the rotor, the stator voltage equations are written under the

Following form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_d \\ v_q \end{bmatrix} = R_s \begin{bmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \end{bmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} L_d & 0 \\ 0 & L_q \end{pmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \end{bmatrix} + p\Omega_r \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \phi_f \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.21)$$

The electromagnetic torque dynamic characteristics of the PMSM could be presented as :

$$T_{em} = p(\phi_d i_q - \phi_q i_d) = p(\phi_f - (L_q - L_d)i_d)i_q \quad (2.22)$$

For a smooth rotor ($L_d = L_q$) this equation becomes:

$$T_{em} = p\phi_f i_q \quad (2.23)$$

2.2.4 Nonlinear dynamic state model of an PMSM

The variables to use are determined by the goals, either for the control or the observation [6]. The identification of the vector states X, U, and Y serves as the foundation for state modeling. The

output vector is made up of the stator currents i_d and i_q , whereas the input vector is defined by the stator voltages V_d and V_q of the MSAP. Depending on the operation's goal, the state vector may have three or four state variables. The system below describes the nonlinear state model in the rotating frame d-q in the event of a torque or angular velocity regulation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \\ \Omega_r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R_s}{L_d} i_d + \frac{pL_q}{L_d} i_q \Omega_r \\ -\frac{R_s}{L_q} i_q - \frac{pL_d}{L_q} i_d \Omega_r - \frac{p\phi_f}{L_q} \Omega_r \\ \frac{p\phi_f}{J} i_q - \frac{p(L_q - L_d)}{J} i_d i_q - \frac{1}{J} T_L \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{L_d} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{L_q} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_d \\ v_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.24)$$

The nonlinearity of this model is due to the terms $i_q \Omega_r$, $i_d \Omega_r$ and $i_d i_q$. For the control of the MSAP dedicated to the regulation of the θ position of the rotor, a fourth state variable must be added as in the following state model:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \\ \Omega_r \\ \theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R_s}{L_d} i_d + \frac{pL_q}{L_d} i_q \Omega_r \\ -\frac{R_s}{L_q} i_q - \frac{pL_d}{L_q} i_d \Omega_r - \frac{p\phi_f}{L_q} \Omega_r \\ \frac{p\phi_f}{J} i_q - \frac{p(L_q - L_d)}{J} i_d i_q - \frac{1}{J} T_L \\ p\Omega_r \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{L_d} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{L_q} \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_d \\ v_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.25)$$

For smooth rotor PMSM ($L_d = L_q = L$), the model becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \\ \Omega_r \\ \theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R_s}{L_d} i_d + p i_q \Omega_r \\ -\frac{R_s}{L_q} i_q - p i_d \Omega_r - \frac{p\phi_f}{L_q} \Omega_r \\ \frac{p\phi_f}{J} i_q - \frac{1}{J} T_L \\ p\Omega_r \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{L_d} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{L_q} \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_d \\ v_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.26)$$

2.3 Three-Phase Inverter

Power electronics converters called inverters change a supply of DC voltage or current into a single phase, three phases, variable amplitude, or variable frequency AC voltage or AC current. Inverters are used in a variety of systems, such as electric power transmission systems, renewable energy sources, and ac motor drive systems.

Figure 2-4 Three-phase full-bridge inverter topology

Inverters can be classified as voltage source inverters (VSI) or current source inverters depending on the type of input source they use (CSI). Three groups of single phase full bridge inverters, single phase H-bridge inverters, and single phase full bridge inverters can also be made from them.

Using six switches ($S_a, S_b, S_c, \bar{S}_a, \bar{S}_b, \bar{S}_c$), a DC constant voltage source (V_{dc}), and a three-phase load (PMSM), Figure 2.4 shows a two-level, three-phase voltage source inverter. The main objective of these topologies is to provide a three-phase voltage source that can control the magnitude, phase, and frequency of the voltage. For a three-phase inverter, the switches on an arm have complementary controls. As a result, each arm has two autonomous states. A boolean magnitude can be thought of as these two states:

- $S_{a,b,c} = 1$: Half-arm switch up (a,b or c) closed.
- $S_{a,b,c} = 0$: Low arm switch (a,b or c) closed.

To simplify the study, the following should be assumed:

- Transistor switching is instantaneous.
- The voltage drop across the terminals of the switches is neglected.
- The three-phase load is balanced, star coupled with isolated neutral.

Figure 2.4 depicts a three phase inverter's power circuit implemented utilizing three insulated arms with two switches each.

A recovery diode is attached to each switch in reverse parallel. Transistors k1 and k4, k2 and k5, and k3 and k6 should be complementary regulated in order to maintain the continuity of alternating currents and eliminate the short circuit of the source; Nevertheless, depending on the power and switching characteristics of the inverter, other semiconductor switches may be used. Consequently, with the specified inverter topology, the following equations hold:

$$v_{as} = v_{a0} - v_{s0} \quad (2.27)$$

$$v_{bs} = v_{b0} - v_{s0} \quad (2.28)$$

$$v_{cs} = v_{c0} - v_{s0} \quad (2.29)$$

Where v_{as} , v_{bs} , and v_{cs} are the phase-to-neutral voltages.

Then

$$v_{as} + v_{bs} + v_{cs} = v_{a0} + v_{b0} - 3v_{s0} \quad (2.30)$$

Assuming that the system is balanced operation

$$v_{as} + v_{bs} + v_{cs} = 0 \quad (2.31)$$

$$v_{as} = \frac{2v_{a0} - v_{b0} - v_{c0}}{3} \quad (2.32)$$

$$v_{bs} = \frac{2v_{b0} - v_{c0} - v_{a0}}{3} \quad (2.32)$$

$$v_{cs} = \frac{2v_{c0} - v_{a0} - v_{b0}}{3} \quad (2.33)$$

2.4 PV Cell Modeling

Numerous components are included in photovoltaic systems that are necessary to power

dependable applications. There are two basic categories into which photovoltaic systems can be divided: standalone and grid-connected solar photovoltaic systems. Figure 2.5 shows a description of these categories by function.

Figure 2-5 PV systems types

Different PV configurations are available that can be used for independent and grid-connected PV system applications. It is clear that the utility grid availability is the primary distinction between these two basic types.

Figure 2-6 Equivalent model of a PV cell

Temperature and sun insolation both directly affect how much current the PV array produces.

The following equations regulate the PV- generated current in figure 2.6 above:

$$I_{pv} = I_m + I_{sh} \quad (2.34)$$

Where, I_{sh} is the current of the shunt resistor defined as:

$$I_{sh} = \left(\frac{V + I_{pv}R_s}{R_p} \right) \quad (2.35)$$

$$I_m = I_g - I_d \quad (2.36)$$

Where, I_g is the PV current generated given by:

$$I_g = (I_{g,n} + K_1\Delta T) \frac{G}{G_n} \quad (2.37)$$

I_d being the diode current given as follows:

$$I_d = I_0 \left(\exp \left(\frac{V + I_{pv}R_s}{V_{t,n}} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (2.38)$$

I_0 being the diode reverse saturation current :

$$I_0 = \frac{I_{sc,n} + K_1\Delta T}{\exp \left(\left(\frac{V_{oc,n} + K_v\Delta T}{\alpha V_t} \right) \right) - 1} \quad (2.39)$$

Where, V_t is voltage in terms of temperature given by:

$$V_t = \frac{N_s K T}{q} \quad (2.40)$$

The output current generated by the PV cell is expressed as:

$$I_{pv} = I_g - I_0 \left(\exp \left(\frac{V + I_{pv} R_s}{V_{t,n}} \right) - 1 \right) - \left(\frac{V + I_{pv} R_s}{R_p} \right) \quad (2.41)$$

2.5 Pumping subsystem modeling

PV pump systems employ a variety of pumps. In this instance, a centrifugal pump is taken into account. This kind of pump is easy to use and requires little upkeep. A centrifugal pump is a mechanical device that uses centrifugal force to convert mechanical energy into fluid pressure. It is very efficient and capable of pumping a lot of water [73]. The torque of the pump and the squared speed of the rotor are inversely proportional.

$$T_L = K_p \Omega_r^2 \quad (2.42)$$

where

$$K_p = \frac{P_{np}}{\Omega_{rn}^3} \quad (2.43)$$

The head of the pump and the amount of mechanical force that may be applied to its revolving impeller dictate water flow and pressure. Calculating the output characteristics of the pump may be made easier by affinity laws, which just need the pump ratings and the actual input parameters, rotor speed and torque [72].

$$\begin{aligned} H' &= \left(\frac{\Omega_r}{\Omega_{rn}} \right)^2 H \\ Q' &= \left(\frac{\Omega_r}{\Omega_{rn}} \right) Q \\ P' &= \left(\frac{\Omega_r}{\Omega_{rn}} \right)^3 P \end{aligned} \quad (2.44)$$

where H , Q and P are the pump's rated characteristics when it is operating at its rated speed Ω_{rn} , H' , Q' and P' are the pump's rated parameters when it is operating at a speed Ω_r that is lower than the

rated speed.

2.6 MPPT Techniques

As was covered in Chapter 1, several techniques have been developed in recent years to find MPP. The number of sensors required, the cost, the rate of convergence, the complexity, the useful range, the proper tracking of irradiance and/or temperature changes, the hardware required for implementation or broad use are only a few of the many ways that these approaches vary from one another. The MPPT control is a method that allows the PV generator to run at maximum efficiency while paying less attention to the temperature, irradiance, and other aspects of the environment. The MPPT controller needs to check the electrical voltage of the solar panel. Its objective is to establish the maximum output current of the panel. Afterward, always make sure to use all of this strength. Among the several MPPT techniques, the P&O technique is the algorithm that is most frequently utilized.

2.6.1 Perturb and Observe

Due to its low cost and ease of use, the P&O is a popular option for PV MPPT approaches. This method's basic operation depends on calculating the PV power using measured PV voltage and current values. Then, by comparing them to the previous power, the direction of the P&O algorithm is addressed. The flowchart below illustrates the various processes of the P&O approach.

Figure 2-7. The standard P&O algorithm's flowchart

2.6.2 Simulation and Results

The output power of PV panels is significantly influenced by the temperature and sun irradiation. The incident global irradiance G and ambient temperature T were measured every 15 minutes using real data from [47]. On a typical August day, Figure 2.8 shows the hourly variation in temperature and solar radiation intensity in Kairouan from 07:00 to 18:00.

The minimum sun irradiance was 130.5 w/m^2 at 7:00, while the average solar irradiance is significantly greater during this time, averaging 997 W/m^2 from 11:30 to 16:00. A abrupt, very brief blockage of the solar disk by excessively thick clouds may be the cause of the low intensity of solar radiation. High sun irradiation typically results in high temperatures. As seen in this figure, the low solar irradiation intensity of 130.50 w/m^2 resulted in an ambient temperature of $16 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the early morning. With rising sun irradiation during the experimental day, the ambient temperature starts to increase. The average temperature for a day was $33.21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, whereas the maximum ambient temperature was determined to be 997 w/m^2 by $43 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 2-8. Temperature and solar irradiation for an average day in August

Figure 2-9. Test system of PV modules

On our PV modules, we performed experimental tests. The analysis of the current-voltage (I-V) and power-voltage (P-V) curves of PV panel output performance characteristics based on various temperatures and sun irradiation is shown in Figure 2.9. Figure 2.10 displays the characteristics of the I-V and P-V curves of PV panels at various ambient temperatures under a constant solar irradiation

$G=1000 \text{ w/m}^2$. The solar irradiation and temperature increase in direct proportion to one another, and this causes the PV power to drop. The two figures' analysis revealed that as the temperature increased, the output voltage would gradually decrease.

However, the output current of the solar panel only varies very minimally with temperature. The output power was noted to decrease by around 5w in these figures for every 10 °C increase in temperature. Based on an analysis of these data, a PV panel's minimum output power at a temperature of 55 °C was 6100 w. When the temperature of the PV panel was lowered to 5 °C, it reached its peak at 7430 w.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2-10 A 3D surface of the characteristic of PV panel at constant 1000 Wm² solar irradiance with different temperatures

At a constant 25°C temperature, the graph demonstrated that when solar irradiation rose, the current and voltage increased as well. Additionally, solar radiation has a crucial role in how much power PV modules produce. The maximum output powers have increased together with an increase in solar irradiation, as can be seen in this figure. Maximum power of 6900 w, was found to have the highest solar irradiance of 1000 w/m², and output power was seen to be in worse condition at low solar irradiance. The lowest measured power was 5100 w, at low level.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2-11. A 3D surface of the PV panel's characteristics at constant 25 °C and various sun irradiances

Figure 2-12 P&O controller for PV motor pumping system.

To assess the efficacy of the conventional Perturb and Observe MPPT method, a Matlab-Simulink model for a single water pumping system was developed. This PV system includes a PV array, a DC-AC inverter with an MPPT controller, a PMSM, and a centrifugal pump, as illustrated in figure 2.12. The main components of the PV pumping system are listed in table B.1. Figure 2.13 depicts the simulated scenario. The solar irradiance input used in this simulation rapidly increased from 100 to 400 and then to 700 W/m².

Throughout the temperature operation, a constant temperature of 20 °C was kept. Figure 2.14, which also displays the dynamic performance of the PV current, PV voltage, and PV power, illustrates how the operating power points diverge from the peak power when the solar irradiation changes rapidly at the times of 3s and

6s. To get back to the maximum power operating point, the P&O changes the control variables. The MPPT adjusts the DC-AC inverter's previous power in response to changes in irradiation by changing the PWM input.

Figure 2-13. Solar irradiance

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2.14 PV Array output for the conventional P&O method under a various solar irradiation levels:
 (a) voltage, (b) current, and (c) power

(a)

(b)

Figure 2-15 Phase voltage and current

(a)

(b)

Figure 2-16 q-axis and d-axis voltage and current

Figure 2-17 Output torque

Figure 2.18 Reference and PMSM speeds

Starting with Figure 2.18 and 2.16, the variations in motor speed and stator currents are shown. From 60, 70, and 50 rad/s, the reference speed was modified to the new value. Vector control employing the q-axis reference current I_q resulted in a decrease in the stator currents. The P&O

algorithm's extracted power and tracking speed were sufficient. However, the results showed instability since the MPP's instability led to more oscillations.

A popular method for tracking the peak power of PV systems is the Perturb and Observe algorithm. P&O separates the MPP from other components of the system by simply altering the PV output voltage and current. Power extraction by P&O is effective, but it ignores system stability.

2.7 Conclusion

Modeling and control of PV systems are covered in this chapter. Finally, the modeling of photovoltaic cells is presented together with an explanation of the fundamental structure and control mechanism of the photovoltaic system. The discussion of conventional P&O MPPTs is followed by a presentation and comparison of simulation results. The efficacy, stability, dependability, and quality of the output system under a variety of environmental conditions can all be improved by employing MPPT with solar systems. This issue is not avoided by conventional P&O MPPT, nor is oscillation eliminated.

3

Chapter 03: Implementation of MPPT controller by Artificial Intelligence

TABLE OF CONTENT

3.1	Introduction.....	43
3.2	Background of Neural Networks.....	43
3.3	The Proposed ANN Model	45
3.2.1	Collection of Data	46
3.2.2	Selection of ANN architecture.....	47
3.2.3	Training the network	51
3.2.4	Testing and validation.....	51
3.4	Simulation Results	51
3.5	Conclusion	59

3.1 Introduction

The P&O MPPT is a popular PV-MPPT approach because of its low cost and simple implementation, as was explained in chapter 2. It struggles with a number of issues, though, including a slower rate of convergence, significant oscillations around an MPP, and a poor capacity to capture the locations where the maximum power may be produced under various meteorological conditions with rapidly changing irradiance.

Numerous efforts using cutting-edge techniques have been made in this direction. Machine learning techniques used in artificial intelligence have received recent attention. One of the most well-known machine learning (ML) systems is artificial neural networks. It has been conceivable to apply ANN to solar energy systems over the past twenty years. ANNs that can handle exceedingly nonlinear relationships and numerical or analog data are typically robust when it comes to finding the best fit solutions [61]. Additionally, users do not need to have strong mathematical abilities.

This chapter discusses the recommended MPPT control configuration for the PV water pumping system. It is supported by a synthetic neural network. A brief historical review of neural networks is presented in the chapter's opening. The well-known artificial neuron's fundamental structure was shown. This chapter also covers the operating concepts of ANN, such as testing and learning. The P&O and ANN are also compared using a typical simulation model and the same atmospheric conditions.

3.2 Neural Networks Background

Nearly everyone among us uses machine learning in daily life, namely the Netflix, YouTube, and digital assistants like Amazon Alexa that offer recommendations. A machine can forecast results, automatically learn from data, and enhance performance over time with the use of machine learning. In order to create the final machine learning algorithm, the ML process starts by entering the learning data into an algorithm. One of the most well-known ML systems is neural networks; these systems or pieces of software are based on how neurons in the human brain work.

Artificial neural networks, also referred to as control, identification, classification, grouping, and other processes, are specially applied to neural networks. A straightforward representation of an artificial neuron is shown in Figure 3.1. The network's numerous inputs are denoted by the mathematical symbol $x(n)$. Each of these inputs is multiplied by a connection weight, $w(n)$. Only in

the simplest scenario are these products combined; the transfer function is then used to calculate the outcome, which is then output. This approach is well suited for practical implementation on a large scale at tiny scales.

Figure 3-1 A basic artificial neuron

Artificial neural networks are typically depicted as signal-exchanging networks of interconnected "neurons." To help neural networks respond to inputs and learn new information, the linkages include numerical weights that can be adjusted over time based on experience.

Data processing structures called neural networks imitate how the brain and biological nervous system function. Within it, connecting nodes or neurons are placed in deeply linked layers.

Information is sent from the input layer to the concealed layer. To transfer the output to the next level, just multiply the output by the weight at each level, add the bias, and then apply an activation function to the result. We will modify the weights and biases of the neurons in a neural network based on the output error. Activation functions enable backpropagation by providing gradients and errors for updating weights and biases. To understand how a neural network works, consider the perceptron as its most fundamental architecture. The neural network of this type lacks cycles (it is a forward propagation neural network).

In its most basic form, the perceptron is a monolayer device with a single output that is linked to each input. A bias unit (b) can be added to the perceptron's initial layer of neurons, which are shown in figure 3.1. Each of these neurons correlates to one of the input variables and allows data to be read. A single, unique output neuron receives the connections from all other units and is given the sum of

the units linked to it, weighted by connection weights. Assuming n variables, X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n . The output therefore receives: $b + \sum_{j=1}^n W_j X_j$. The output neuron then applies an activation function to this output. A perceptron therefore predicts thanks to an activation function F defined by:

$$Y = F \left(b + \sum_{j=1}^n W_j X_j \right) \quad (3.45)$$

3.3 The Proposed ANN Model

The integrated pump system typically consists of five basic components, as indicated in Figure 3.2: the PV array, DC-AC inverter with an MPPT controller, PMSM, and centrifugal pump.

Figure 3-2 Proposed ANN controller for PV motor pumping system.

Four types of artificial neural networks are proposed for the control bloc PV motor pumping system. The goal of Multilayer Perceptron (MLPs) is to foresee the PV array's highest power point in order to simultaneously improve power extraction and decrease system instability.

3.2.1 Collection of Data

The initial step in creating an ANN is gathering data (inputs, outputs). Increasing the amount of data available improves the efficiency of ANN. These data was collected from simulation using a Matlab-Simulink model by P&O technique in Chapter 2. Where they inputs are: ϵ_{Ω} is the angular reference speed error, $\epsilon_{v_{dc}}$ output generator DC voltage error, ϵ_{i_d} and ϵ_{i_q} are the dq-axis PMSM current error as depicted in tables 3.1 Each table shows the inputs and outputs of an ANN. The inputs are represented by a 100001x1 matrix, which is static data made up of 100001 samples of 1 element. A 100001x1 matrix, or 100001 samples of 1 element, is the output.

State	Input ϵ_{Ω} (rad/s)	Output i_{qref} (A)
1	60	30.64
2	59,96	30.63
3	59,84	30.62
4	58.13	30.56
5	57.57	30.38
⋮	⋮	⋮
100000	-9.63	5.26
100001	-9.66	5.25

(a)

State	Input $\epsilon_{v_{dc}}$ (V)	Output i_{dref} (A)
1	-125	-65.4
2	-124.31	-57
3	-122.28	-51.7
4	-118.96	-47.6
5	-114.45	-44.5
⋮	⋮	⋮
100000	-0.83	-0.029
100001	-0.84	-0.028

(b)

State	Input ε_{i_d} (A)	Output v_{dref} (V)
1	-161	-124
2	-97	-90
3	-73	-65
4	-53.47	-47
5	-30	-33
⋮	⋮	⋮
100000	0.0014	-0.0036
100001	0.001	-0.0041

(c)

State	Input ε_{i_q} (A)	Output v_{qref} (V)
1	30	300
2	30.12	300.6
3	30.18	301
4	30.24	302
5	30.48	303
⋮	⋮	⋮
100000	-2.97	-22.37
100001	-3.14	-22.74

(d)

Table 3.1. : Samples data's from the conventional method used in the Chapter2 test

3.2.2 Selection of ANN architecture

Results are affected by network architecture. Before choosing a neural network topology, the network's network type, number of layers, neurons per layer, and activation functions must all be configured. The necessary layers and neurons must be adjusted until the desired outcome is attained because there is currently no recommendation for computing their values.

Figure 3-3. ANN_Current_Reference q-axis PMSM

The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) network we used to begin has three layers, as shown in figure 3.3.

- The first layer: the input is the reference angular speed ϵ_{Ω} , as shown in equation 3.2 the mapminmax function used in the ANN structure is used to normalize input values.

$$mapminmax = \frac{(x - x_{min})(x_{max} - x_{min})}{(y_{max} - y_{min})} + y_{min} \quad (3.46)$$

- The second layer (the hidden layer): consists of 10 hidden neurons that convey data to the output layer from the input layer. Its activation functions are the rectified linear activation function (ReLU) is seen in equation 3.3.

$$RELU(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x < 0 \\ x & \text{if } x \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (47.3)$$

- The third layer (the output layer): contains one neuron which is the d-axis PMSM current reference (i_{dref}). The activation function is linear function (Purelin) and the normalized values are converted to their normal values using the mapminmax_reverse function in Equation 3.4.

$$\text{mapminmax_rever} = \frac{(x - y_{\min})(x_{\max} - x_{\min})}{(y_{\max} - y_{\min})} + x_{\min} \quad (3.48)$$

$$\text{purelin}(n) = n \quad (3.49)$$

Figure 3-4 ANN_Current_Reference d-axis PMSM

A MLP with two hidden layers, the activation functions ReLU and tansig at the first and second hidden levels, the d-axis PMSM current reference output, the i_{dref} generator, as well as the ϵ_{vdc} generator DC voltage error input. The tansig activation function calculates its according to:

$$\text{tansig} = \frac{2}{e^{-2x} + 1} - 1 \quad (3.50)$$

(a)

(b)

Figure 3-5. ANN_Voltage_Reference dq-axis and d-axis PMSM

As shown in Figures. 3.5 (a) and (b), two MLPs with the same architecture, the networks is created with a single neuron in the input and the output, and 20 neurons in the hidden layers.

3.2.3 Network training

After the design of the ANNs and the establishment of data collecting, training is made possible. The model was developed using the Trainlm function available in the ANN toolbox as the supervised training strategy for the ANN-MPPT controller. An MLPs feed forward network is created using a Matlab m-file and the newff tool. The Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) backpropagation method is optimized by the network training function Trainlm to update weights and bias values. The error criterion taken into account during training is mean square error (MSE). Epochs, objective, and show are the training parameters for trainlm. During training, the trainlm training parameters are adhered to as shown below. Using the gensim (net) command, a neural network simulink block is generated when the network has been built.

3.2.4 Testing and validation

Testing and validating the network is the last step before using it. Testing our machine learning model on data that has not been used for training is the proper technique to assess its performance. Therefore, we randomly divide the dataset into three groups: a subset of 80% is used for training the MLP, 10% for validating the model, and the remaining 10% is used for testing the resulting model, which assesses the performance of the model.

3.4 Simulation Results

To decrease system instability and enhance power extraction from the PV system simultaneously, an MPPT based on artificial neural networks with four cascaded ANNs is used. The conclusion we reached is based on a certain amount of temperature $T = 20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and irradiance levels $G = 200\text{ watt/m}^2$, which were modified to simulations of 400 and 700 watt/m² under the identical circumstances as in Chapter 2 to get our conclusion.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 3-6. The training regression results for ANN-MPPT control

In order to perform a linear regression between the network outputs and the appropriate targets, the test data set is fed into the network. This will enable us to examine how the MLPs networks respond. Regression analysis is then used to compare the network response to the pertinent targets. The network's output (predicted power extraction) and corresponding targets (calculated power extraction) are then provided to the linear regression analysis function. Figure 3.6 displays the three different parameters it produces for each network: a, b, c, and d. One is the ideal value of R, which denotes a close relationship. The parameter R denotes the correlation between the desired output and the expected output of the network. The correlation between the desired output and the network's predicted output is represented by the parameter R. The points in 3.6. a, b, c, and d are practically on the best regression line, indicating that both networks predict the power extraction for the training data set quite well.

(a)

Figure 3-7 Performance of PMSM for various reference speeds: case 1

For ANN current reference q-axis on a (a) epoch 200000 and (b) with epoch 500000

(b)

Figure 3-8 Performance of PMSM for various reference speeds: case 2

For ANN current reference d-axis on a (a) epoch 100000 and (b) with epoch 200000

(a)

(b)

Figure 3-9 Performance of PMSM for various reference speeds: case 3

For ANN voltage reference dq-axis on a (a) epoch 100000 and (b) with epoch 500000

Figure 3-10 Performance of PMSM for various reference speeds: case 4

For ANN voltage reference d-axis on epoch 100000

Figure 3.10 illustrates the final outcome of numerous training sessions, which was a satisfying outcome. As can be seen, there is a good agreement between the angular reference speed and the motor's angular speed. Significant simulation results of the control law, PV extracted power, PV voltage, dq-axis PMSM current, and tracking error are presented to prove the value of the proposed control technique.

Figure 3-11 torque

Figure 3-12 Performances of the PV system compared between MPPT with P&O and the suggested ANN approach

The proposed ANNs-based technique has the maximum efficiency because there is little power supply ripple. It turns out that the ability to simultaneously track the maximum power point and system stability makes the proposed method perform better than the standard method.

3.5 Conclusion

The configuration of the suggested ANN-based MPPT control for the PV water pumping system is covered in this chapter. We constructed a PV motor pumping system and used machine learning technologies to develop a real-world application for it. In the control bloc PV motor pumping system, we employed ML.

We demonstrated the many steps involved in setting up the learning base and configuring the MLP-style artificial neural network. The results of a study that compared the conventional MPPT P&O with our suggested ANN technology showed that our method concurrently increased power extraction and system stability.

GENERAL CONCLUSION

Effectiveness, stability, and dependability of a photovoltaic energy source are viewed as being important determinants in the development of this energy source. In this study, common maximum power point tracking methods such as perturb and observe and artificial neural networks have been suggested to increase the output power of freestanding solar water pump systems. Enhancing the stability of a PV power conversion has also been an aim, especially in the context of shifting meteorological conditions.

The following are the study's overall findings: employing a solar array to model and research the features of the motor and pump in a standalone MPPT-powered photovoltaic water pumping system. To establish which approach is best for the system, many types of MPPT methods are also studied. Analyzing the impacts of insolation and temperature fluctuations on the output characteristics of solar arrays can help you learn how to optimize energy capture and delivery to loads.

To develop a potent ANN MPPT approach that will improve the performance of standalone PV water pumping systems. To assess performance at various PV irradiance levels, system components are first individually modeled in Matlab-Simulink and then coupled. A comparison is made between the ANN MPPT method and the conventional P&O MPPT algorithm. The results show that the ANN MPPT operates with a more stable system, a quicker dynamic responsiveness, and better power extraction. Simulator models were developed and used in this study to examine the efficacy of the MPPT procedures that were proposed. To validate the simulation results, however, actual hardware tests must be carried out at a representative power level and in the typical environmental circumstances of an application. The simulation results obtained in this work should encourage further research into developing prototype models to test the suggested MPPT algorithms for the PV water pumping system experimentally.

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Appendix A

Standalone PV water pumping system's Simulink model

Figure A-1 The Simulink model based standalone PV water pumping system

Appendix B

Table B.1 Parameters of the PV pumping system.

PV array	Values (STC)
Number of cells in series (n_s)	10
Cells resistances of PV (R)	415 Ω
Nominal power (P_n)	185 w
Open circuit voltage (V_{oc})	30.2 V
Maximum power voltage (V_{mp})	24 V
Short circuit current (I_{oc})	8.54 A
Maximum power current (I_{mp})	7.71 A
Temperature Coefficient of P_{max}	-0.485%/ $^{\circ}C$
Temperature Coefficient of I_{sc}	+0.053%/ $^{\circ}C$
Temperature Coefficient of V_{oc}	-104 mV/ $^{\circ}C$
Type of PV cell	Monocrystalline
Type of PV module	Sharp NU-S5E3E 185
Conversion Efficiency	14.1%
Inverter	Nominal values
Inductance (L)	10 mH
Capacitance (C)	1110 μF
Capacitance Input (C_{in})	1110 μF
the diode quality factor (A)	1000
PMSM	Nominal values
Efficiency	86.1%
d -axis inductance (L_d)	0.011 H
q -axis inductance (L_q)	0.011 H
Stator resistance (R_s)	20.5 Ω
Rotor resistance (R_r)	14.45 Ω

Magnetizing inductance (L_m)	0.921 H
Inertia (J)	0.00095 kg m²
Viscous friction coefficient (F)	1e-4 N m/(rad/s)
Number of pole (p)	3
Centrifugal pump	Nominal values
Pumping flow (Q)	0.08–0.58 l/s
Pumping head	5–19.5m

Appendix C

Data sheet of Sharp NU-S5E3E 185 PV module

SHARP

NUS5E3E / NU185E1
185 W

Photovoltaic module monocrystalline

MONOCRYSTALLINE SILICON PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULE WITH 185 W NOMINAL POWER

Sharp's NUS5E3E / NU185E1 photovoltaic module is designed for large electrical power requirements. Based on the technology of crystal silicon solar cells cultivated for over 40 years, this module has superb durability to withstand rigorous operating conditions and is suitable for grid connected systems.

Features

- High-power module (185 W) using 155.5 mm square monocrystalline silicon solar cells with 14.1 % module conversion efficiency.
- Photovoltaic module with bypass diode minimises the power drop caused by shade. Textured cell surface to reduce the reflection of sunlight and BSF (Back Surface Field) structure to improve cell conversion efficiency.
- Using white tempered glass, EVA resin, and a weather-proof film along with an aluminium frame for extended outdoor use.
- Output terminal: Lead wire with waterproof connector.
- NUS5E3E: manufactured in Japan
NU185E1: manufactured in UK
Apart from the place of manufacture the models are identical in construction.
- Hail damage resistance tested by TÜV in accordance with IEC61215.

Specifications NUS5E3E / NU185E1

Cell	Monocrystalline silicon solar cells, 155.5 mm square
No. of cells and connections	48 in series
Maximum system voltage	1,000 V DC
Nominal power	185 W
Dimensions	1,318 x 994 x 46 mm
Weight	16.0 kg
Type of output terminal	Lead wire with connector

Ambient conditions

Parameters	Rating	Unit
Operating temperature	-40 to +90	°C
Storage temperature	-40 to +90	°C
Storage humidity	up to 90	%

Temperature coefficients

αP_m	-0.485% / °C
αI_{sc}	+0.053% / °C
αV_{oc}	-104 mV / °C

Electrical data

Parameters	Symbol	Min.	Typ.	Unit
Open circuit voltage	V_{oc}	—	30.2	V
Maximum power voltage	V_{pm}	—	24.0	V
Short circuit current	I_{sc}	—	8.54	A
Maximum power current	I_{pm}	—	7.71	A
Nominal power	P_m	175.8	185.0	W
Module efficiency	η_m	—	14.1	%

The electrical data applies under Standard Test Conditions (STC): Radiation 1,000 W/m² with a spectrum of AM 1.5 and at a cell temperature of 25 °C.

Characteristics

Current, power vs. voltage characteristics
(cell temperature: 25 °C)

Open circuit voltage, short circuit current
vs. irradiance characteristics
(cell temperature: 25 °C)

Nominal I_{sc} , V_{oc} , P_m vs. cell
temperature characteristics

Outline dimensions

A-A' Cross section

B-B' Cross section

Application options

- Grid connected residential systems
- Office buildings
- Solar power stations
- Solar villages
- Villas, mountain cottages
- Lighting equipment
- Traffic signs
- Radio relay stations
- Beacons
- Telemeter systems
- Telecommunication systems

This module should not be connected to any direct load.

In the absence of confirmation by specification sheets, Sharp takes no responsibility for any defects that may occur in equipment using any Sharp products shown in catalogs, data books, etc. Contact Sharp in order to obtain the latest specification sheets before using any Sharp products.

Specifications are subject to change without notice.

